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Building stock modelling for circularity: Insights from a Danish component-level model

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the iBuildGreen building stock model, which estimates the material content of the Danish building stock based on macro-component archetypes (types of wall, roof, floor slab, etc). The model draws up a detailed material inventory and estimates the embodied carbon content for each building, based on publicly available Danish National Building Registry data. The high level of detail provides new insights for urban mining and life cycle assessment. The model is first tested for the municipality of Odense, and the results are then compared to the case of Copenhagen. The model is also compared with other archetype models, in terms of output and relevance as a decision-support tool.

1. Background

About 37 % of global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are attributed to buildings and construction activities (Cabeza et al., 2022; United Nations Environment Programme, 2024). The sector is also a major consumer of non-renewable resources, such as river sand, steel, and aluminium (Deetman et al., 2020). For the building sector to develop within the safe operating space defined by the planetary boundaries, a profound transformation of how buildings are constructed, used, maintained, and demolished is needed (Richardson et al., 2023). This requires changes across multiple scales, from national policymaking to local planning, to detailed design, material choice and waste management decisions in individual projects. In many ways, Denmark has been at the forefront of this transition. The country has been among the first to introduce mandatory limits for climate impact in new construction projects in 2023, and initiatives such as a “reduction roadmap” setting voluntary targets for the impact of new construction projects have seen broad support (Balouktsi et al., 2024; Reduction Roadmap Consortium, 2022). However, these limits and targets focus largely on climate impact and primarily influence decisions at the project level. To support sustainable urban planning and policymaking, a broader perspective is needed.

Recently, there has been increasing interest in circular strategies as a way of addressing these challenges. Public authorities at local, regional, and national levels consider that a better understanding of their material

stocks and flows can enable sustainable resource management and unlock opportunities for impact mitigation (Cartwright et al., 2020). Building-stock models play an important role in supporting strategic planning for sustainability. They can help identify resource needs linked with new construction and renovation and can estimate flows of construction and demolition waste. Such information is essential to develop circularity strategies, such as dimensioning infrastructure for waste treatment and recycling, matching the future demand for construction materials with the available reusable resources, identifying impact hotspots, and evaluating target fulfilment.

Building-stock models and studies can be classified broadly as top-down or bottom-up. Top-down studies rely on input-models or material flow analysis (MFA) to provide insights into resource flows at the level of the whole building stock or for an entire economic sector (Augiseau & Barles, 2017). They are comprehensive but are often unable to provide results with a high level of detail. Conversely, bottom-up studies focus on modelling the properties and material content of individual buildings and aggregating that information to provide insights on a larger scale. In turn, bottom-up studies can be classified as archetype-based or component-based. Archetype-based modelling has commonly been used in studies analysing the material content of the building stock (e.g. Augiseau & Kim, 2021; Oezdemir et al., 2017). Each building is mapped on to a particular archetype, usually based on its use type (single family house, apartment building, office, etc.) and its year of construction. Each archetype is associated with material intensity

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coefficients (MICs) describing the amounts of various materials based on the building's dimensions, usually per m² of floor area (Heeren & Fishman, 2019). These MICs are derived from case studies of "typical" buildings for each archetype. For Denmark, one notable archetype-based building stock study was carried out by Lanau & Liu (2020) for the municipality of Odense. "Block-wise MICs", describing the building's material content in the roof, slabs, vertical elements, and underground elements respectively, were derived based on case studies of buildings corresponding to each archetype from the European TABULA project (Loga et al., 2016). This study has been taken further in more recent publications, such as the study by Ohms et al. (2024), which developed MICs for specific university buildings. While building archetypes offer a simple approach to link the properties of buildings with their material content, the level of detail and disaggregation they offer still limits their usefulness. MICs defined as total amounts of concrete, clay, etc. do not provide detailed enough information for applications related to circularity. For instance, identifying reuse opportunities requires knowing how much concrete consists of prefabricated wall panels as opposed to foundations, whether the clay products are bricks or roof tiles, etc. Furthermore, MICs based on archetypes are limited in respect of which building categories they can accurately cover. While they might provide accurate estimates for buildings that closely resemble their archetypes, they struggle to reflect the broad diversity of the building stock in terms of design and material choices, regional variations in architectural style, or the influence of building geometry on material content (height, compactness, etc.). The more a building differs from one of the model's archetypes, the less accurate the model's estimates will be.

Component-based models attempt to bridge this gap by generating a more detailed material inventory for each building, based on the available data on various building properties. Their higher resolution entails more complex and data-intensive modelling rules. A notable example is the French BTP-Flux model (Tirado et al., 2021), which makes use of the large amount of data available in the French national building database (BDNB), combined with a database of components and macro-components (TyPy) and a model deriving a building's geometry from geospatial data. Recent research has also considered the possibility of using remote-sensing technology such as satellite and street-view data to obtain more fine-grained, building-specific information and improve model precision and accuracy (Arbabi et al., 2022). Overall, opportunities offered by component-based models remain relatively unexplored. Since the amount and quality of available data influences modelling possibilities, these opportunities are also highly dependent on the country. This paper presents a new component-level model developed for Danish building stock: the iBuildGreen model. It contributes to the further understanding of Denmark's historical building stock and examines highly granular building-stock models, their usefulness, and their limitations. The study's objectives are as follows:

1. Develop a model that can estimate a detailed material inventory for Danish buildings based on publicly available information.
2. Draw up a material inventory and embodied carbon-replacement costs for the existing building stock in the municipalities of Odense and Copenhagen.
3. Compare model results for the two municipalities and compare them with previous studies of Odense.
4. Discuss the relevance of the model in monitoring urban mining and building stock.

2. Method

2.1. Preliminary data gathering

2.1.1. The national building registry (BBR)

Denmark benefits from a relatively extensive and publicly accessible database of existing buildings and their properties: the national registry

of buildings and housing (BBR). This first implementation of the iBuildGreen model uses the following parameters from the registry: information on each building's use, year of construction, footprint, gross floor area and number of floors, as well as roof and façade material.

The BBR database theoretically includes information on every single building in Denmark. However, while it contains a lot of useful information, it also has some incorrect entries. The first step in implementing the model was therefore the importation and pre-processing of BBR data in order to remove obviously incorrect entries. First, entries from which key parameters were missing (year of construction, roof and façade material) were deleted, as were duplicate entries, and entries with negative values for the floor area or number of floors. Some problematic outliers were deleted as well. Large values for footprint and floor areas do not necessarily represent wrong data: some high-rise buildings, warehouses and agricultural facilities are indeed very large. However, some cases clearly represented mistakes in data entry and were deleted (e.g. buildings where the number of floors is equal to the footprint or the floor area, or higher than the number of floors for the tallest skyscraper in Denmark). About 5 % of buildings in the database have a footprint and floor area under 10 m². These values might be correct for small annexes such as carports and sheds, but are likely to be incorrect for conventional building types such as detached houses. Such buildings were therefore deleted. Finally, for buildings where the footprint (or respectively the floor area) was incorrectly entered (e.g. value missing or equal to 1), the missing value was approximated using the number of floors and the floor area (or respectively the footprint). The pre-processing removed close to 16 % of database entries, corresponding to 12 % of the reported gross floor area.

2.1.2. Cataloguing historical design practices

Beside the building registry, the other essential source of information in modelling the material content in the existing stock pertains to common design solutions for various components, depending on the building type and time period. Most previous studies attempting to model the material content of the existing stock rely on building-level archetypes, where typical material intensity coefficients are derived for buildings of various types and time periods (Augiseau & Kim, 2021; Heeren & Fishman, 2019; Lanau & Liu, 2020; Oezdemir et al., 2017). The iBuildGreen macro-component model attempts to provide a finer grained description of the building stock and its diversity by instead modelling archetypes at the level of the macro-components (types of roofs, walls, slabs, etc.). A building is therefore described as a combination of macro-components, each determined based on the building's properties.

Prior to the iBuildGreen model's implementation, a catalogue of macro-components commonly used in various time periods in Denmark was developed. The main source of information for this exercise was a study of historical building design in Denmark (Engelmark, 2013). Archives of design handbooks were also consulted (Bonnesen, 1971; Nissen, 1984). This resulted in a catalogue of typical solutions for internal and external walls, floor slabs, foundations, roof structures and roof covers, each defined by a time period during which it was typically used, a typical amount of various construction products (per m² of wall, roof, etc.), and other important properties (such as minimum and maximum viable roof pitch for each type of roof). An example is given in Fig. 1. The full catalogue of components is provided as supplementary information.

When implementing the catalogue of macro-components, each product was mapped with a corresponding generic product found in the Danish building life-cycle assessment (LCA) tool LCAByg (Kanafani et al., 2021). These generic products and the corresponding emission factors are based either on industry-branch EPDs or on the German generic environmental database Ökobau. Linking the model with background environmental data from the LCAByg tool offers opportunities to assess the embodied carbon replacement cost of the existing stock, and the potential climate benefits of reusing components. The carbon replacement cost corresponds to the embodied climate impact

Fig. 1. Example of macro-components from the iBuildGreen catalogue, linked with LCA data from LCAByg.

that would be caused if all buildings in the existing stock were constructed today (Lanau et al., 2021; Müller et al., 2013). The embodied carbon replacement cost does not account for the evolution of emission factors for various construction materials over time using present emission factors instead. The integration with LCAByg also confers a great flexibility on the model. Since this linking can be automated, the model can easily be updated to match new versions of the background environmental data, such as the introduction of environmental data that is compliant with the recent EN 15804+A2 norm. This compatibility enables the two tools to be integrated permits the creation or modification of macro-components based on LCAByg data, allowing incremental improvements to the model.

2.2. Model design and implementation

The iBuildGreen macro-component model is implemented via a PostgreSQL relational database and a Python logic layer. The database stores information from the BBR registry, the catalogue of components, and the model's results. Mapping tables in the database are used to link buildings with macro-component types, and macro-components with sub-components. For example, a "building to roof" table links each building with a type of roof. The Python code interacts with and modifies the PostgreSQL database, and is used to perform all calculations and logic operations.

The model estimates a material inventory for the full building stock in several successive steps. Fig. 2 illustrates the procedure in the case of

Fig. 2. Illustration of the quantification of material amounts in the external walls of a building.

external walls. First, information from BBR is used to provide “best guess” estimates of which types of macro-components are used in each building. In this first version of the model, this estimate is only based on the façade and roof cover materials recorded in BBR, as well as the building’s construction year. For components for which relevant information is directly available (roof cover, roof structure and external walls), the range of possible solutions is first narrowed down to macro-components that fit the recorded material type. For instance, if the recorded façade material is “brick”, the external walls could be massive brick walls, sandwich walls or curtain walls. Then the remaining solutions are filtered further based on the building’s year of construction. If this year fits within the periods of use for several solutions, one is selected at random. Similarly, in the rare cases where the year of construction does not fit the use period of any solution, a random solution is selected.

After associating each building with a macro-component type for each building part, material amounts are quantified using a dimensioning procedure. In the absence of more precise data about building dimensions, the height of each building is estimated based on the number of floors and a standard floor-height value. The roof pitch is estimated based on the type of roof cover material. Functions for dimensioning inner walls were extrapolated from French studies (Mailhac, 2019). While it would be preferable to use dimensioning functions derived from Danish studies, to the authors’ knowledge such studies do not yet exist. The study by Mailhac (2019) represents a rigorous attempt at linking the surface of inner walls in a building to its floor area, and the Danish building stock was assumed to be similar enough to the French stock to use the same functions. A future update to the model could use functions derived specifically for Danish buildings, when such functions become available. The perimeter of the building is estimated based on the footprint and a space efficiency factor to correct for the fact that the building’s footprint is not a rectangle. Once these building dimensions have been estimated, material amounts are calculated based on typical material amounts for each type of component (usually per m² of wall, roof, etc.) recorded in the macro-components catalogue. A last set of functions allows the database for results in a specific municipality to be queried, sorted by material type or building part, etc.

2.3. Application to Odense and Copenhagen

The model generates an estimated material inventory for every single building in the pre-processed building registry. To illustrate the capabilities of the model, the results are presented for the municipality of Odense. Odense is the third largest municipality in Denmark. It is a particularly relevant example for illustrating the model because it has been covered by several previous studies of building stock (Lanau et al., 2021; Lanau & Liu, 2020; Li et al., 2022). This allows a comparison between the model’s results and previous studies of the same municipality. Additionally, the model is also implemented in the case of Copenhagen, the capital of Denmark, in order to illustrate the differences between municipalities. To the authors’ knowledge, this study constitutes the first material mapping of Copenhagen’s full building stock. Although the model provides detailed inventories specific to each building, the results are presented aggregated by type of material and building element. To enable a comparison with previous MICs for various building archetypes developed by Lanau & Liu (2020) in the case of Odense, median and average results are also presented for the same archetype categories even though the iBuildGreen model does not use building archetypes. Each archetype is a combination of a building type and a construction period, corresponding to shifts in architectural practices or building regulations in Denmark (e.g. “apartment building 1960-1972”).

3. Model results and analysis

3.1. Estimated material amounts and embodied carbon for Odense

Fig. 3 shows the total material amounts in the building stock for the municipality of Odense, broken down per building element and material type. A spatial visualisation is provided in Fig. A1, available in the Appendix. An alternative visualisation comparing building elements is provided in Fig. A4 in the Appendix.

The modelled material content of the building stock is mostly dominated by concrete, with clay as the second most widespread material. The predominance of concrete can be explained by its widespread use in foundations and ground-floor slabs, meaning that it represents a large volume in most buildings. It is noteworthy that the foundations represent the largest material-use hotspots according to the model, but they are also one of the greatest sources of uncertainty. Material amount estimates for the foundations are coarse and conservative, defined as generic material amounts per m² of building footprint. In reality, they depend considerably on the location and soil conditions, as well as the building’s height compared with neighbouring properties. The map provided in Fig. A1 in the Appendix indicates a few clusters with a high concentration of building materials throughout the municipality, particularly around the harbour and the historical city centre. The overall distribution is polycentric, and the municipality also includes areas with very little material stock. This is because the administrative boundaries of the municipality go beyond the Odense urban area to include agricultural areas as well.

The high resolution of the material inventories provided by the model enables insights that would not be available using a model based on broader building archetypes and coarser material categories. For instance, a closer investigation of the “clay” material category shows that over 70 % of this category corresponds to bricks in external walls, 15 % to bricks in internal walls and only 2 % to roof tiles. The prevalence of brick façades in Denmark offers an opportunity to reuse bricks for facing. Similarly, the model does not simply estimate total amounts of concrete, but also in what form and which building parts this concrete can be found. The model estimates that most concrete by far is found in the foundations and ground-floor slabs of buildings. These elements cannot be disassembled, so the only viable strategy to make use of these existing resources is to preserve or retrofit existing buildings instead of demolishing them. Precast concrete elements, aerated and lightweight concrete blocks, and concrete roof tiles make up less than 10 % of the total amount of concrete, but they provide interesting mitigation opportunities due to their high potential for disassembly and reuse. Roughly half of these potentially reusable concrete elements are found in internal walls. Therefore, the reuse of precast concrete panels in internal walls would be a relevant priority for circular strategies. This illustrates the relevance of working with a high-resolution model when the focus is on circularity and reusability.

By linking the estimated inventory of construction products in the existing stock with background environmental data from the LCAByg tool, the iBuildGreen tool also calculated the embodied carbon replacement cost of Odense’s building stock, as illustrated in Fig. 4. An alternative visualisation comparing building elements is provided in Fig. A4 in the Appendix. The analysis covers the production of all construction products in the city’s existing stock, as well as their treatment and disposal at the end of life (modules A1-A3 and C3-C4 according to the EN 15804 terminology). A similar analysis could be carried out for other environmental impact categories within the EN 15804 framework, for example, acidification potential, eutrophication potential and ozone depletion.

The calculated carbon replacement cost of Odense’s building stock is 6.5 MtCO_{2e}. While concrete still represents the largest hotspot in terms of embodied carbon replacement cost, clay represents a higher proportion of the impact compared to the previous analysis by weight. This is particularly noteworthy for internal and external walls, where bricks

Fig. 3. Total material amounts estimated for Odense municipality in kg, per material type and building element. The inset shows the percentile distribution of various building elements for materials with a small total amount.

represent the largest hotspot due to the high climate impact of their production. Insulation materials also represent a larger share of the impact compared to their relatively small weight. A separate consideration of the impacts of material production (modules A1-A3 of the life cycle) and disposal (modules C3-C4) shows a rather different picture, in particular when it comes to the impact of wood products. The environmental data for wood products used in LCAByy follows the “-1/+1” accounting convention for biogenic carbon, where carbon absorbed during tree growth is counted as a carbon sink in modules A1-A3, and is released at the end of life in module C3 (Ouellet-Plamondon et al., 2023). Following this accounting method, the embodied carbon replacement “cost” linked with the production of new biogenic construction products is actually negative, but the cost of handling (and usually incinerating) waste biogenic products after demolition corresponds to almost 87 % of the impact linked with modules C3-C4. This draws attention to the important role played by existing buildings as biogenic carbon sinks. However, it should be noted that this analysis based on attributional LCA data for wood products does not consider all the potential consequences of a large-scale demand for timber (such as the limited availability of sustainably harvested timber and changes in forest carbon stocks (see Hansen et al., 2024).

3.2. Comparison between Copenhagen and Odense

Quantities of material in the municipality of Copenhagen are given in

Fig. 5, and a spatial visualisation is provided in Fig. A2 in the Appendix. An alternative visualisation comparing building elements is provided in Fig. A6 in the Appendix. While Copenhagen is a much larger city than Odense, the administrative boundaries of the Copenhagen municipality exclude a significant portion of the urban area, while Odense municipality encompasses the entire city of Odense and its rural surroundings. As a result, material amounts in the municipality of Copenhagen are only marginally larger than in the municipality of Odense. A comparison of the model results for Odense and Copenhagen shows significant differences. In Copenhagen, internal walls are the main hotspot of material use in terms of weight and embodied carbon, with foundations coming second: recall that foundations were the main hotspot in Odense. This can be explained by the fact that the model uses uniform material quantities per m² of footprint for the foundations. Buildings are significantly higher in Copenhagen, and therefore a larger share of materials is found in internal and external walls. The spatial distribution within Copenhagen municipality is much denser than in the case of Odense because Copenhagen municipality consists almost exclusively of urban spaces. The only low-density areas correspond to green areas (notably a nature reserve in the south), as well as the airport in the south-east. The empty area close to the centre of the map corresponds to Frederiksberg, an administratively distinct municipality.

The distribution of various building types and construction periods is very different between the two municipalities. Copenhagen is dominated by apartment buildings built between 1850 and 1930 (26 % of the

Fig. 4. Estimated carbon replacement cost of Odense’s building stock, i.e. embodied emissions from the demolition of existing buildings (modules C3-C4 of the life cycle) and their replacement with similar buildings (modules A1-A3 of the life cycle taking present-day emission factors into account). The inset shows the percentile distribution of the various building elements, for materials with small carbon replacement cost.

gross floor area), followed by apartment buildings built from 1931 to 1950 (12 % of the floor area), apartments built after 2007 (7 % of the floor area) and office buildings built before 1930 (5 % of the floor area). Overall, 61 % of the stock in Copenhagen consists of apartment buildings, 18 % of offices and only 6 % of detached and row houses. Odense shows a much flatter distribution of archetypes, with a high proportion of single-family houses built from 1960 to 1972 (6 % of the floor area), as well as offices built in the 1970s, 80s and 90s (7 % of the floor area). The stock in Odense comprises 17 % of apartment buildings, 15 % of offices and 32 % of detached and row houses. At the national level, the composition of the stock is very varied, with about one third of detached and row houses, 13 % of apartments, 21 % of agricultural and industrial facilities, and 20 % of buildings in the “others” category corresponding to carparks, garages and sheds etc. Material quantities per m² for various archetypes also differ between the two municipalities. This can be explained by differences in building properties. For instance, the median floor area of detached houses is significantly smaller in Copenhagen than in Odense, and the opposite is true for apartment buildings. This affects the relative importance of walls, floor slabs, foundations, etc. in the overall material inventory.

There are also significant differences in the distribution of façade and roof materials between the two municipalities. In both cities, brick façades dominate, although this is even more pronounced in Copenhagen, with close to 80 % of buildings floor area having a brick façade compared to 68 % in Odense. Roof materials show more diversity in both municipalities. Copenhagen shows a higher prevalence of roofing felt and tiles. Both materials are also widespread in Odense, but Odense shows a much higher proportion of concrete compared with Copenhagen. It is noteworthy that 9 % of buildings in Odense are reported as

having a glass façade compared to 1 % in Copenhagen, and similarly for glass roofs. A closer look at the building registry indicates that the higher prevalence of glass façades and roofs in Odense is caused by several large greenhouses used for agricultural production. This therefore does not reflect an actual difference in buildings such as houses and offices.

3.3. Comparison of model predictions

Fig. 6 shows the distributions of estimated material amounts per m² gross floor area for two of the most widespread building categories, aggregated by material type. The figure also includes the corresponding MICs from a previous study of Danish building stock by Lanau & Liu (2020), for purposes of comparison. The spatial visualisation in Figure A3 in the Appendix shows areas for which the iBuildGreen model provides lower or higher estimates respectively than Lanau & Liu’s model in the case of Odense.

Significant differences can be seen between the two models. The macro-component model often underestimates material amounts for the most common building archetypes (i.e. houses and apartment buildings constructed before the mid-20th century). However, the macro-component model tends to provide higher estimates for more modern buildings. This is reflected in spatial patterns: the iBuildGreen model provides lower estimates in Odense’s historical city centre, but higher estimates in newer peripheral development areas. An earlier comparison between results from the iBuildGreen model and a small sample of buildings indicated that the iBuildGreen model provides good estimates for walls but tends to underestimate material amounts in the roof and floor slabs (Francart et al., 2023). One possible explanation is that stairs, balconies and attics have not yet been properly modelled. Foundations

Fig. 5. Estimated material amounts in Copenhagen municipality, in kg, per material type and building element. The inset shows the percentile distribution of the various building elements, for materials with small total amount.

also represent one of the most important sources of variability and one of the most important differences between the models.

Regarding assessments of embodied carbon, Lanau et al. (2021) estimated the carbon replacement value of Odense’s building stock (excluding infrastructure) at around 9.2 MtCO_{2e}. The estimate provided by the macro-component model is of the same order of magnitude, but lower. This is consistent with the previous observation that estimates of material amounts for the most widespread building archetypes are lower in the macro-component model than in Lanau’s study.

4. Discussion

4.1. Model accuracy and future improvements

This study proposes a novel model for predicting the material quantities available in Denmark’s building stock. The model which is based on predefined macro-components derived from the literature, provides more granular information on the materials used in various building types constructed across different periods. Building on a bottom-up approach, it allows the calculation of material quantities at different spatial scales—such as neighbourhoods, municipalities, or the entire country—although in this study, we focused on the municipalities of Odense and Copenhagen. The iBuildGreen model can be considered a refinement of the previously published model by Lanau and Liu (2020), with greater potential to enhance the accuracy and robustness of material stock predictions. Additionally, the model delivers results at the component and material level, an essential requirement for enabling circular economy strategies. However, it is important to note that the model relies on several additional assumptions, which influence the results obtained.

The data-preprocessing steps handled the most obvious wrong entries in the registry, but they do not guarantee that the remaining data are correct. The “cleaned” registry still had a significant number of entries with questionable values, which could not be detected during preprocessing. The considerable number of excluded entries - 16 % of entries for 12 % of floor area - means that estimates of the full material content at the city level are probably underestimated, but the data-cleaning steps lead to better estimates for the typical material content of the various building types.

The two main sources of data exclusion were a missing year of construction and unconventional entries for façade or roof materials (e.g. façade material missing or marked as “other”). An important step in improving the model further is therefore to handle these cases. The data could be enriched using for instance, remote-sensing (satellite images, street view, etc.) to obtain missing data on roof and façade materials and verify existing data (Arbabi et al., 2022). This would also provide more accurate information on building geometry. Missing values for the construction year could be derived from an analysis of historical maps and plans at the municipal level (Li et al., 2022). The ongoing development of material passports and better information on construction and demolition waste will also offer opportunities to improve model predictions incrementally by systematically comparing them with measured data.

In cases where building information is complete and reliable, the model can be improved through more thorough rules for dimensioning elements. The BBR registry includes some relevant parameters which have not yet been integrated into dimensioning rules, such as the year of last renovation, area of integrated parking, presence of asbestos, etc. These parameters could help provide more accurate estimates. The overall estimates of material quantities are considerably influenced by

Fig. 6. Distribution of modelled material intensities for two of the most widespread building categories: single-family houses built 1961-1972 (top), and apartment buildings built 1850-1930 (bottom). Red lines are median values, red dots average values. Each grey dot represents one building in the registry. Green dots represent MICs from Lanau & Liu (2020), for comparison.

dimensioning rules for foundations and ground-floor slabs, although these estimates are less important when focusing on which elements have the potential to be reused. The first implementation of the model uses relatively simplistic dimensioning rules for these elements, based on material amounts per m^2 footprint, but real material amounts in the foundations are heavily dependent on the building's location, height, type, etc. While data from real cases is limited, a set of 60 LCA studies of modern Danish buildings by Zimmermann et al. (2020) suggests that material amounts in foundations might be better correlated with the gross floor area than with the footprint (although the correlation remains weak).

In this first version of the model, components such as basements, stairs and balconies were not modelled separately. Furthermore, interdependences between components have not been implemented. These rules could be based, for example, on the respectively components' load-bearing properties: thus "a floor slab of type A is incompatible with walls of type B". Dimensioning rules could be improved over time by creating a body of case studies. Similar models such as the French BTP-Flux (Tirado et al., 2021) have benefited from previous studies analysing, for example, the frequency of use of various components in the French building stock and the typical surface of internal walls depending on the building geometry. Such knowledge is not

available for the Danish stock but could offer an opportunity to improve the model's accuracy.

Finally, a major challenge and point of improvement concerns the modelling of non-residential buildings which differ from residential buildings in their geometry and the type of components typically used in their construction. These aspects were largely ignored in this first version of the model (except for the modelling of inner walls, which considers building type). A better consideration of non-residential buildings offers considerable opportunities to improve the model. However, this is particularly challenging, because non-residential buildings are much less standardised than residential buildings: they differ considerably between building types (a hospital and a cinema are very different) and within building types (two concert halls might have very different geometries and components). This was identified as a major issue for the development of MICs for non-residential buildings by Lanau & Liu (2020). Despite the limitations of this study, the iBuildGreen model offers a higher level of granularity compared to Lanau and Liu' model (2020), which operates at the building archetype level. While archetype-based models are grounded in real case studies, our model incorporates a broader and more detailed set of building components. The limited availability of measured data on the material content of buildings makes it difficult to compare the relative accuracy of the two models; however, such data may become more widely available with the adoption of material passports and material audits during building decommissioning. Both modelling approaches should be seen as complementary, each contributing valuable insights that future research can build upon to improve material stock predictions. Whereas Lanau and Liu's model quantifies the total amount of materials in the building stock, the iBuildGreen model extends these predictions to the component level, offering more specific and actionable information essential for enabling circularity, and making it more suitable for strategic planning and urban mining due to its finer resolution. However, further validation is necessary. Cross-checking iBuildGreen results against audits of demolished buildings would improve confidence in the model. Enhancing the underlying component database through the analysis of real case studies could also refine the model's accuracy. Moreover, incorporating uncertainty analysis to provide ranges of possible material quantities would further strengthen predictions at the whole-building scale. To support circularity efforts more effectively, material and component information should also include data on dimensions, mechanical properties, the presence of hazardous substances, and the degree of degradation—factors that depend on prior usage conditions and lifespan—before reuse in new construction.

4.2. External validity and applicability to other countries

The iBuildGreen model was developed using data for the Danish context. The macro-components used are heavily tied to historical architectural practices in Denmark, and the structure of the model fits the available data from the Danish BBR registry. Therefore, the iBuildGreen model in its current implementation can be used to model building stocks in any area of Denmark, and its implementation is easily scalable from individual neighbourhoods to the entire country. However, the model cannot easily be applied to other countries, as it would need to be adapted to fit other national building registries. This is not simply an issue of mapping appropriate parameters from one country to another. Indeed, the availability of building-stock data varies considerably between countries, and the amount and quality of available data influence the level of accuracy and precision the model can achieve (Cartwright et al., 2020). For instance, France also has an extensive national building registry, enabling the implementation of similar models, while Sweden has no such national registry because most of its building data is managed at the municipal level. This would create considerable challenges to the implementation of a similar national model. In the future, remote sensing technology might provide opportunities to develop building-stock models even in countries where

important parameters are unavailable (Arbabi et al., 2022). Finally, some countries might present regional differences in architectural practices. In such cases, the macro-component catalogue would need to be adapted not only to the national level, but also to each relevant region.

4.3. Addressing existing barriers to circularity

The primary purposes of developing a building-stock model at the component level are to provide decision support, show the value of preserving existing buildings and components, facilitate reuse, and address barriers to circularity. Existing barriers to reuse in Denmark were catalogued by Koch-Ørvad et al. (2023), based on a review of the scientific literature and a series of case studies. The following categories of barriers were identified:

- Regulatory barriers: complex regulatory landscape, with an unclear division of responsibilities for waste-handling and a lack of harmonised requirements or guidelines.
- Documentation barriers: lack of best-practice knowledge and documentation regarding the properties of reused materials (load capacities, fire safety, etc.). Conventional engineering heuristics cannot be used. This also makes it difficult to find insurance for reused products.
- Infrastructure and logistical barriers: lack of facilities to transport, store and control materials safely before reuse; complex supply chain for reused products.
- Process barriers: poor waste-handling strategies within projects, and high cost and time pressures.
- Behavioural barriers: conservative and risk-averse thinking, and lack of experience with reuse.
- Design and technical barriers: difficulties in matching specifications between reused products and new needs (element length, height, thermal properties, etc.).
- Business and market barriers: financial risk and small market for reuse. Each project requires specific investments that are rarely transferable or scalable.
- Contractual barriers: early design choices might constrain product choices later on. Procurement processes are rigid, and contracts are rarely written in a way that accommodates reuse.

The high granularity of results in the component-level model should facilitate the mapping of materials for waste management, and the identification of reuse opportunities. It could therefore help planning authorities prioritise, locate and dimension waste handling facilities, addressing infrastructural barriers. The model could also help identify business opportunities by predicting the supply of reused products and matching it with the demand for new construction. For property managers and demolition companies, such a model could assist in mapping the material content of buildings prior to deconstruction and help solve process barriers. However, these potential use cases would require improvements to reach a higher degree of both precision and accuracy. In particular, process-, design- and documentation barriers require highly specific knowledge on the dimensions and properties of reusable products. This would require improvements in the dimensioning rules used by the model and the possible use of complementary sources of data such as remote-sensing (Arbabi et al., 2022). Addressing other barriers to reuse will require a closer consideration of the needs of relevant decision-makers. At this stage, time-consuming case-by-case assessments of the material content of buildings and the residual properties of reusable products remain unavoidable. Still, a component-based model can be a useful tool for the planning and prioritisation of circularity measures.

The integration of environmental data from the LCAByy tool into the iBuildGreen model also enables a granular assessment of embodied carbon replacement costs for existing buildings, and of the

environmental benefits of reusing various building components. A future use-case for the modelling making use of these resources, would be to quantify the environmental benefits of reuse and circularity strategies to support strategic planning at the municipal level. In particular, the iBuildGreen model could be combined with future scenarios for construction and demolition to forecast the various quantities of the components required for new construction that can be made available from demolished buildings and to quantify the savings that could be achieved by matching the demand with the available reusable resources. However, such modelling can only be a small part of the solution, as many of the barriers to circularity concern other process-related aspects. Furthermore, reusing materials requires a very detailed knowledge of their properties (exact dimensions, remaining structural properties, etc.). The iBuildGreen model is therefore useful as a tool for scoping and prioritising circularity strategies, but it needs to be complemented by other approaches to implement circularity measures in practice.

5. Conclusion

The iBuildGreen building-stock model is able to provide highly granular inventories of building products for any building where accurate information is available in the Danish building registry. This unlocks useful information for strategic planning related to circularity in the building sector. In particular, the model can be used to estimate the amounts of various construction products that might be needed for new construction and that might be made available in decommissioned buildings and identify opportunities to match the material demand with the supply of reused products. Through the integration of environmental data from the LCByg tool, the iBuildGreen model can directly estimate the environmental benefits of reusing particular components, as well as calculate an embodied carbon replacement cost for the existing stock.

While the iBuildGreen model provides valuable insights and a high level of detail, its accuracy is limited by the dimensioning rules used in the model and the quality of available data. The model is therefore more detailed, but not necessarily more accurate than previous building stock models. There is often a trade-off between precision, accuracy, and breadth of coverage in the choice of a model. The relevance of any model for decision support depends on the question it is meant to answer. To quantify total amounts of, for example the concrete or metal in a municipality, a model based on building archetypes with a lower level of detail is appropriate. To assess renovation needs for a particular building, a high level of both precision and accuracy is necessary, and purpose-built archetypes covering only a narrow building type are relevant (Kanafani et al., 2022). But to identify more specific reuse opportunities, plan for circularity strategies and urban mining and calculate the environmental benefits, a granular model is needed.

There is also a need for more harmonised modelling approaches and data. The iBuildGreen model, in its nomenclature and implementation, remains highly specific to Denmark and would require a significant amount of work to be translated to other countries. Data availability also varies tremendously between cities and countries (Cartwright et al., 2020). In other countries with less available building stock data, the first step to implement such a model would either be to develop a thorough national building database or to fill these data gaps using remote-sensing data (Arbabi et al., 2022).

Supplementary information

The following supplementary information is available alongside this article:

- Open-source code for the iBuildGreen model: <https://github.com/NFrancart/iBuildGreen>
- Macro-component catalogue.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

N. Francart: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **S.R.B. Gummidi:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Conceptualization. **E. Hoxha:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration. **H. Birgisdottir:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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